

Fostering Developmental Local Government (DLG) for Effective Local Economic Development (LED) Implementation: A Case of the Polokwane Local Municipality (PLM)

Maela Khutso Delphus¹, Munzhedzi Pandelani Harry², and Mathebula Ntwanano Erasmus³
Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa^{1,2}
*School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg, South Africa*³

The paper examines the importance of Developmental Local Government in implementing Local Economic Development in Polokwane Local Municipality. The paper continually argues that DLG plays an effective role in implementing LED strategy in South African local government. It is thus important for the Polokwane Local Municipality to rely more on DLG which helps in facilitating LED for effective service delivery. The study is limited to PLK. The paper adopted mixed methods for collecting data to support the proposed argument. Closed-ended questionnaires and structured interviews were used as techniques for data collection. Thematic and statistical analysis was applied in this paper to analyse the findings. The study population was based on traditional leaders, councilors, selected community members, municipal officials, and community stakeholders within the PLM area. The paper discovered that DLG can foster community participation, effective municipal policies, effective service delivery, support the informal traders, effective infrastructure development, and local capacity building through LED projects. Therefore, the paper recommends that the PLM should invest more in or capacitate DLG as it is effective in fostering the LED project implementation. The paper recommends further studies on DLG and LED implementation in the local government of South Africa. This paper proposes sustainable developmental local economic stimuli theory (SDLEST) on the application of below principles: community-stakeholder participation, public/community value, utilisation of local resources, job creation, accountability measures, local education and training, participative NGOs, regional investors, and empowerment.

Keywords: development, local economic development, Polokwane local municipality, local government

The paper examines the efficacy of DLG in implementing the LED strategy in PLM in Limpopo Province. The DLG is a result of complex socioeconomic and political processes such as democratization, marketization, and decentralization (Schoburgh & Chakrabarti, 2016: 21). As stated by Sebola, Tsheola, Phago, and Balkaran (2016:05) and Maela (2021:42) local government is regarded as a sphere of the government that is close to the communities and ensures that citizens partake in service delivery process, governance as well as socio-economic development sustainability which are significant for job creation of the people. Koma (2014) discourses LED as an important tool for enhancing economies at the local level and addressing the high rates of unemployment, inequities, and poverty that communities experience. Additionally, Nkwini and Munzhedzi (2016:76) and Rogerson and Nel (2016) highlight LED

as a 'place-based' strategy for development at the local level.

Local economic development strategy recently gained recognition at the grassroots level, particularly in underdeveloped countries (Kahika & Karyeija, 2017:159; Gamede, 2020:388). Local economic development strategy has advanced throughout the past years and is now extensively recognised as the development, organizations or agencies, policymakers, and governments throughout the world (Shilangu, 2019:632; Mabunda & Ndou, 2019:347). The DLG can ensure that all community members have equal access to municipal basic services and that all can engage in decision-making processes and planning so that the economies at the local level can increase to ensure job opportunities and resources at the local level are wisely used with the intent to improve the well-being and general welfare of the communities.

The White Paper on Local Government (1998) provides the following characteristics of DLG: maximising social development and economic growth; integrating and coordinating development planning; promoting democratic development; and building social capital at the local level to enable local solutions to development challenges (White Paper on Local Government, 1998).

Theoretical Foundation

To support and guide this paper, governance theory was adopted as a foundation as it later directs us to local governance for relevancy. Therefore, local governance theory as derived from governance serves as the foundation for this paper. Governance values transparency, participation, openness, and the rule of law. Local governance, as asserted by Nissen (2020) is about power,

Author Note

¹Maela Khutso Delphus, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa

²Munzhedzi Pandelani Harry, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa

³Mathebula Ntwanano Erasmus, School of Public Management Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg South Africa

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Maela Khutso Delphus, Department of Public and Development Administration, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa
E-mail: khutso.maela@univen.ac.za

relationships, and accountability. It tackles issues like decision-making authority and accountability. Furthermore, Koma (2012) argues that modern local government expectations must extend beyond the fundamentals of service provision. Tobi and Oikhala (2021) also briefly characterize local governments as democratic, decentralized organizations. Kaywood (2021) added that local governance serves as a means for individuals and organizations to express their views and communicate with government agencies and one another.

Ramodula and Govender (2023:1554) contend that the essence of South African DLG originates from the constitutional stipulations regarding local government as a distinct realm of governance. For instance, local governments have naturally adopted the South African concept of a developmental state, which is primarily concerned with economic growth. According to Ramodula and Govender (2020:6061), and Ramodula and Govender (2023), DLG entails a local government that collaborates with local communities and other stakeholders to develop sustainable strategies for enhancing socioeconomic well-being in general and, therefore, living standards.

For this paper, the local governance theory is relevant to the DLG since it encourages the local communities of PLM to be involved in the activities of the municipality and be able to submit their needs. The local governance theory is vital for encouraging the delivery of the basic needs of the community. It encourages the municipality in making the policies or laws to consider the participation of the community to ensure that their needs are submitted, prioritised, and converted to output. The DLG is responsible for good governance in the local municipality; therefore, the concept of local governance theory encourages governance in the municipality through participation.

Unpacking Developmental Local Government

According to Mello (2020), DLG is seen as a solution to South Africa's deep-seated structural socioeconomic difficulties. While Mathebula (2016) and Ramodula and Govender (2023) suggest that the vision of a DLG is one of the most proposed ideas for defining the constitutional mandate of local government in the post-apartheid era, the vision remains too abstract and perhaps too distant from the realities of local authorities. Mello (2020:6-8); Chakwizira, Peter, and Thompson (2021); and Pieterse (2023) argue that interpreting the DLG as the local developmental state is necessary since the distinguishing qualities are developmental state tenets.

Localisation of Developmental Local Government: Practise

Maximizing Social Development and Economic Growth

Koma (2012:56-57) and Auriacombe and Van der Waldt (2020) discourse that municipalities can achieve social development and economic growth by implementing practical LED strategies to support small, medium, and micro-enterprises development as well as business retention, expansion, and attraction. Furthermore, Auriacombe and Van der Waldt (2020) argue that municipal governments are not directly responsible for employment creation. The White Paper on Local Government, 1998, emphasizes that local governments must put more effort into ensuring that the general social and economic conditions of the people are favorable for

creating job opportunities. The local government as stated by the White Paper on Local Government, 1998, may also encourage social development by providing arts and culture, recreational and social welfare services, and public resources. The municipalities are mandated by the constitution to provide grants to associations and childcare resources. Empowering marginalized and underprivileged populations contributes significantly to social progress.

Integrating and Coordinating

Developmental local government through the White Paper on Local Government, 1998, must ensure provisions of leadership and vision to contributors to local development. According to the OECD (2021), inadequate coordination among service providers can seriously harm development efforts. Ntlabezo (2013) asserts that towns should forcefully pursue techniques and methods for ensuring resources and investment from both the private and public sectors to achieve developmental goals. Local government plays an effective and significant role in the provision of basic infrastructure and basic service delivery as discussed by Asha and Makalela (2020). However, Dlamini and Reddy (2018) note that the developmental responsibility entrusted to local government necessitates strong institutional capacity and the use of effective strategic instruments.

Local governments are responsible for providing services that are prioritized, guided by a participatory process, and sustainable as examined by Dlamini and Reddy (2018). The Integrated Development Plan (IDP) is an important technique or tool that compels the local government to provide services effectively and efficiently. The IDP is aimed at enhancing and speeding up the provision of basic services in the municipality as shown by Mathebula (2018). Munzhedzi, Phago, and Mubangizi (2022) and Van der Waldt (2018) add that processes of the IDP and reviews for municipalities should be geared towards working with local communities and respective organisations within those communities intended to sustainably meet their economic, material, and social needs to achieve their general welfare and quality life and coordination. Manzini (2016) opines that the IDP process offers municipalities powerful instruments for facilitating integrated and coordinated service delivery within their areas.

Democratising Development, Empowerment, and Redistribution

Ramolobe (2023) discourse that the main problem that hinders development in local government is the power inequalities between councillors and traditional leaders. Even though there is urgency about service delivery to the represented majority, the traditional leaders and municipalities tend to differ or fail to agree. The municipality and traditional authorities are sometimes unable to agree. Furthermore, Ramolobe (2023) states that local government councils play an important role in developing grassroots democracy. Mawere, Matshidze, Kugara, and Madzivhandila (2022) state that both municipal councillors and traditional leaders are legally permitted to represent the same rural populations, emphasising the necessity of their co-existence as well as the importance of respecting one another regardless of their standing. Mawere et al. (2022) address that in ensuring that people are well represented, the ward councillors should, by all means, ensure that community members are involved in all programmes of local government.

Malemane and Nel-Sanders (2021) in support of the White Paper on Local Government (1998) stated that as per municipalities

citizens are required to engage in four ways; as citizens who express their views before, during, and after the policy development process to ensure that policies reflect, as voters, to ensure maximum democratic accountability of the elected councillors. Battilana, Yen, Ferreras, and Ramarajan (2022) societies throughout the world are facing two interwoven, serious problems: environmental damage and the resulting climatic catastrophe, and a democratic crisis caused by structural and rising inequality.

Human Rights

The Bill of Rights, enshrined in Chapter 2 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) assures that every individual in South Africa has human rights that represent the country's principles of human dignity, equality, and freedom (Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996). Durmus (2020) in support of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) adds that local government participation might be a response to human rights critiques in a variety of ways. Local governments are viewed as ideally positioned to localize human rights and bridge the gap between the universality and cultural relativism poles. Pieterse (2022) states that it is widely understood that local government acts and activities are important for the realization and enjoyment of human rights. Moreover, Pieterse (2022) alludes that cities, towns, and villages are the sites where civil and political rights are performed, where the objects of socio-economic rights are accessed and delivered, and where the participatory dimensions of all rights are actualized. Pieterse (2022) argues that it is also necessary to consider the manner and extent to which municipalities and communities are in turn empowered, both by the constitutional devolution of state power and by the fact of their human rights obligations.

Gender Equity

Vyas-Doorgapersad (2023) claims that gender imbalance is a big issue in South African towns. Furthermore, Vyas-Doorgapersad (2023) believes that local government is responsible for delivering basic services to the communities based on their expectations and wants as they are in the sphere closest to the people. According to Malesa (2023:3), municipalities are characterised by gender inequalities which serve as a challenge that leads to a lack of gender policies, a lack of women's empowerment, limiting women's capacity to contribute to civic life and municipal duties that guide the nation's growth and lack of gender mainstreaming. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2020) gender inequality inhibits women from supporting one another, causing problems in socio-economic development in their communities and requiring the state to deal with additional issues to ensure inclusive governance, which is effective, economically fair and efficient. Jansen (2023:4) discovered that local government fails to involve measures for gender equality in political portfolios, and policy texts, posing significant hurdles and decision-making processes for advancement. This condition is evident in the governmental portfolios, as stated by Shava (2021:909) and corroborated by Malesa (2023:3) who states that women persist in having limited access to top managerial posts.

Leading and Learning

Local government plays a vital role in creating social conditions conducive to growth (Madumo, 2012:46; Koma, 2014). This is

through the following: ensuring free flow and management of information for easy access; enhancing local democracy by creating strong awareness of human rights and constitutional issues; responsive problem-solving and a commitment to working in open partnerships with stakeholders, building awareness on environmental issues and their impacts; investing and building the kind of political leadership capable of bringing different groups and interests together. Municipalities have important roles as policymakers, intellectuals, institutions of local democracy, and innovators. Additionally, municipalities must be responsible or be regarded as learning organizations that mobilize funds and resources to address fundamental needs and attain goals sufficiently.

Developmental Local Government as an Enabler of Local Economic Development: A Relief

Moyo (2021: 24-25) endorsed by Pugalis and Tan (2017:9) proposes that in this LED paradigm, the function of DLG has acquired prominence as a government that has close contact with people and engages with concerns related to local development. The developmental Local Government viewpoint is centered on promoting a place-based and more bottom-up approach to issues of local development (Moyo, 2021:24). This function of local government is consistent with the idea of LED. Furthermore, Thani (2020) and Moyo (2021) noted that the economic and political growth worldwide is increasingly centered on decentralisation, giving DLG a stronger mandate to play an active role in LED. The growth of the local economy demands territorial independence and a sufficient level of autonomy which may be achieved by a decentralized and entrusted type of local administration (Moyo, 2021: 25).

The DLG is an excellent area to develop LED by promoting connections between social capital, resource utilization, and local human capital to leverage problem-solving collaboration to promote the general welfare and people's well-being in each community. As a result, DLG is well-positioned to facilitate local development by encouraging communication and linkages between residents, resources, and opportunities (Pugalis & Tan, 2017:9). According to the International Labour Organization (2020), by connecting local people, resources, and opportunities, local authorities and communities may produce greater jobs and a higher quality of life. In response to globalization issues, local governments and communities are turning to LED initiatives.

Furthermore, the International Labour Organisation (2020) advocates for decentralization, arguing that top-down initiatives supported by the national government and its line ministries frequently lack local-level engagement and are distant rather than context-specific. This is to do a theoretical investigation of how local governments may permit LED. Makhathini, Mlambo, and Mpanza (2020) argue that this analogy of discussion follows the narrative that since LED is identified as a localized planning approach and local government as a locality-oriented government tier, how can it facilitate the prerequisite and enabling conditions for economic development to flourish in line with the local interests of people in the geographical. Central governments delegate authority and responsibility to local governments to satisfy the needs of residents and communities, as well as formulate plans according to local norms and priorities. According to Boledinyane (2022), local government is the sphere of the government that is close to the

public, and they are liable for providing and maintaining public services and infrastructure at the local level.

Method

This paper opted for the application of a pragmatic research paradigm wherein both contextual and descriptive research are used. Interviews and questionnaires are the data collection techniques that were applied to collect the data related to fostering DLG for effective LED strategy implementation in PLM. The study consisted of councilors, municipal officials, traditional leaders, selected community members and community stakeholders within the PLM area. The sample size of the study comprised of 140 respondents. 110 selected community members, 5 councilors, 5 traditional leaders and 10 community stakeholders were given closed-ended questionnaires, while 10 municipal officials were interviewed face to face. This paper was facilitated by the usage of purposive sampling and non-probability sampling. Both qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed through the usage of statistical and thematic analysis. The questionnaire data was analyzed through International Business Machinery: Statistical Product and Service Solutions (IBM: SPSS) the latest Version 28.0. The presentation of information was through the form of graphs, and tables, followed by percentages and frequencies. Thematic analysis was applied to analyze the data collected through interviews. Furthermore, the appointment was made for effective data collection. The questionnaires were given to one hundred and forty respondents. The questionnaire consisted of five (5) Likert-scale responses; namely Strongly Agree, Agree, Not Sure, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. This paper adhered to and followed research ethics. The ethical principles followed were, permission to conduct the study, informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality and anonymity, and no harm to participants.

Data Presentation, Interpretation, and Analysis

The main aim of this paper is to examine the effect of DLG in implementing LED in Polokwane Local Municipality. This section presents, interprets, and analyses quantitative and qualitative data collected from the selected respondents. When examining the effect of DLG in implementing LED in Polokwane Local Municipality, sub-questions were generated for respondents to supplement the main question of the paper. In this paper, 140 questionnaires were distributed, and all were returned. Other respondents took longer than expected, but a researcher remained patient until they were submitted. The researcher used a graphical tabular format, frequencies, and percentages to present the data that was collected through the questionnaires. Each table and graph are followed by a brief discussion of the findings.

Analysis of Data Collected Through Questionnaires

The data in this section is presented in a graphical tabular form which was compiled from the questionnaire items.

Effectiveness of DLG Implementation

In this sub-section, the paper probed whether the DLG is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality to improve the socio-economic development. The presentation was as follows;

Respondents were asked as to whether DLG is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality. The above Figure 1: discovered that 56 (40%) respondents strongly disagreed that DLG

is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality. In addition, 28 (20%) respondents disagreed. Twenty-eight (20%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Furthermore, 14 (10%) respondents agreed and lastly, 14 (10%) respondents were not sure. Most respondents disagreed with the question, wherein few agreed, and others were not sure that DLG is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality. The paper concludes that if these contributing challenges persist the DLG will be ineffective. Therefore, the paper suggests that community participation, education and training, employment creation, and oversight mechanisms be implemented as a way of enforcing DLG in Polokwane Local Municipality.

Figure 1

Effective Implementation of DLG

The Role of DLG in Ensuring Development

In this sub-section, the paper examines whether DLG plays a role in facilitating or ensuring development. The responses were as follows:

Figure 2

The Significance of DLG in Fostering Development

It was probed to the selected respondents as to whether DLG plays an important role in ensuring development. Figure 2: revealed that 84 respondents, which constitute 60%, strongly agreed with the statement, while 28 which constitute 20%, agreed. Twenty-one of the respondents which constitute 15%, disagreed with the statement. Lastly, no respondents were not sure about the statement. Most respondents strongly agreed that DLG plays important role in fostering development. The paper, therefore, suggests that the socio-economic development of the Polokwane Local Municipality can be maintained or promoted through the effective implementation of DLG. The paper concludes that the Polokwane Local Municipality should promote and practise the objectives or values of DLG to alleviate poverty and create employment opportunities.

DLG and Sustainable Development

The paper seeks to gain a deeper understanding of whether DLG works with people in promoting sustainable development in Polokwane Local Municipality. The presentation was as follows

Figure 3

The Realisation of Sustainable Development Through DLG and the Community Member's Contribution

It was probed by the selected respondents as to whether DLG works with people towards sustainable development. Figure 3: presents 63 which constitute 45% strongly agreed with the statement, wherein 35 respondents which constitute 25% agreed. Twenty-eight respondents which constitute 20% strongly disagreed with the statement, wherein seven (7) respondents which constitute 5% disagreed. Lastly, seven respondents which constitute 5% were not sure. Most of the respondents strongly agreed that DLG works with communities towards realisation of sustainable development. The paper suggests that since the DLG is aimed at working with communities towards sustainable development, there is a need to foster community participation in all activities of the municipality. The paper concludes that failure to involve the community members in all activities of the local government will result in poor community development. Moreover, the paper calls for Polokwane Local Municipality to fully involve the community members in municipal policy planning and implementation as a way of shaping community development and fostering sustainable development.

The Role of DLG Regarding Pre-determined Needs of the Community

This paper probed the role of DLG in achieving the predetermined needs of the community. However, the following were the responses.

Figure 4

The Significance of DLG in Meeting Community Needs

It was asked from the selected respondents whether DLG meets the pre-determined needs of the community. Figure 4: revealed that 70 respondents, which constitutes 50% agreed with the statement, wherein 42 which constitutes 30% agreed. Twenty-eight respondents which constitute 20% disagreed with the statement, whereas there were no respondents who strongly disagreed with the statement. Lastly, there was no respondents who were not sure about

the statement. The paper was dominated by the majority of respondents who strongly agreed that DLG meets the pre-determined needs of the community. The conclusion can be drawn from the majority of the respondents who agreed with the statement. The paper therefore, concludes that to meet the predetermined needs of the communities, the Polokwane Local Municipality requires a multi-faceted approach involving community engagement, effective governance structures, strategic planning, resource management, and continuous evaluation.

Capacity Building for LED projects

The paper asked if there is enough capacity for promoting LED through DLG. The presentation was as follows.

Table 1

Capacity Building to Foster LED Projects

Sr.No.	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	70	50%
2	Agree	35	25%
3	Not Sure	7	5%
4	Strongly disagree	7	5%
5	Disagree	21	15%
	Total	140	100%

Table 1: presents the data on the statement that there is enough capacity building for the LED projects. The data indicates that 70 respondents which constitute 50% strongly agreed with the statement that there is enough capacity building to foster LED projects, while 35 respondents which constitute 25% agreed. Twenty-one respondents which constituted 15%, disagreed with the statement, wherein 7 respondents, which constituted 5%, strongly disagreed. Lastly, 7 respondents, which constitutes 5%, were not sure with the statement. The majority of the respondents disagreed that DLG has enough capacity to foster the LED Projects. From the findings, the paper concludes that failure to create jobs, poverty reduction, and adequate service delivery, entails insufficient capacity to foster LED. The paper proposes that through infrastructure investment, business support services, promotion of entrepreneurship, workforce development, support for key sectors, collaboration and partnership, strategic planning, monitoring and evaluation, and local procurement initiatives, DLG can foster LED projects. The Polokwane Local Municipality is therefore advised to build sufficient capacity to foster socio-economic development.

Analysis of Data Collected Through Interviews

This section expresses data conducted through the interviews which were given by the researcher to the participants. Ten respondents were interviewed. The data was presented in a narrative form. The probed question was about the effect of DLG in implementing LED.

Participant A replied that

Concerning the question of effective implementation of DLG. The respondent answered by stating that DLG is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality since the communities around ext.78 (Disteneng) are provided with houses. The provision of houses to the Disteneng communities entails that the DLG is heading towards meeting the well-being of the community of Polokwane Local Municipality. The below picture indicates the houses provided in EXT 78.

Figure 5

Picture of Houses Built by Polokwane Local Municipality at Ext 78 (Disteneng) (Polokwane Local Municipality Idp2023)

Previously known as Disteneng informal settlement).- Good Story to tell for Council EXT 78 Houses under Ward 08 Previously known as Disteneng informal settlement).-

Participant B replied that

In response to the question, the respondent answered by saying that DLG is effectively implemented in the sense that there is economic growth and job creation in Polokwane Local Municipality, which is a significant measure of economic activity, and it is well executed since the Municipality currently advertised posts for local communities to be employed to ensure positive change in the life of people. Additionally, the respondent emphasised that a municipality opted to partner with local stakeholders, businessmen/women, and community forums to address the service delivery problems such as water and fight crime. A municipality is cooperating with the police services and the newly formed community forum or group called Seshego Community Against Crime against Gangsterism (SCACAG). The SCACAG forum also propose effective service delivery by the government to the communities. Therefore, the above-mentioned partnership and collaboration assist in achieving the general welfare of the communities.

Participant C replied that

In an attempt to answer the question, the respondent responded that the DLG at Polokwane Local Municipality is well implemented. However, the increase in population in the Municipality is the reason why the project fails to cater to all the communities. Hence overpopulation and vast migration to cities from rural areas remain the problem in the Polokwane Local municipality.

Participant D replied that

About the question, the respondent answered that the DLG is effectively implemented in PLM in the sense that the below strategic plan is now implemented. the Polokwane Municipality Public Transport Plan, 2007; The Polokwane Municipal Integrated Transport Plan, 2008, Polokwane Local Municipality: Polokwane Local Municipality: CBD Development Plan, 2005 and Compilation of Framework Plan for Strategic Development Areas 1, 2 and 3, 2007. The municipality has Leeto la Polokwane Busses for community members' transportation. The renovation and modification of roads through the EPWP serve as proof of the development projects that seek to attract business opportunities for the municipality and create job opportunities.

Participant E replied that

In response to the question, the respondent emphasised that PLM has been actively implementing LED through DLG to enhance various aspects of infrastructure and community welfare. The

construction of borehole infrastructure and pumping mains for the Sandriver South Wellfield and Polokwane boreholes demonstrates a commitment to improving water access and management within the municipality. The respondent, moreover, added that the provision of essential services such as electricity, water, roads, streetlights, housing, transportation, and job opportunities through the Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP) projects suggests a multifaceted approach towards stimulating development within the municipality.

Participant F: replied that

In an attempt to answer the question, the respondent stated that DLG is practised at Polokwane Local Municipality since the municipality is partnered with other businessmen/women as well as other stakeholders to create jobs and economic growth. The respondent added that the decision to build another Peter Mokaba Stadium impacted the economy of the local municipality and broader Limpopo province. Having teams like Kaizer Chiefs and Supersport United to utilise the stadium as their home ground not only brings in revenue through hosting fees but also attracts visitors from other provinces. This influx of visitors likely boosts various businesses including shops, lodges, resorts, and informal traders who get the opportunity to sell their products at the stadium. Overall, it seems that the stadium serves as a catalyst for economic growth and brings benefits beyond just sports to the local community.

Participant G: replied that

Regarding the stated question, the respondent answered that the projects implemented by the DLG through the LED strategy positively impacted the Seshego area. The construction of the tar road near the Circle Centre aimed at attracting more business to the area seems to have been effective. Additionally, providing boreholes for water access and a delivery system for those unable to access it independently indicates efforts to address a fundamental need within the community.

Participant H: replied that

Responding to the proposed question, the respondent answered that the local government took the step in delivering the Safe Illumination Paraffin Stove Pilot Project (SIPSPP). The initiative taken by the Polokwane Local Municipality in facilitating the Safe Illumination Paraffin Stove Pilot Project seems to be an important step towards addressing safety concerns related to the use of illuminating paraffin in low-income households. The primary goal of the project appears to be twofold: first, to ensure the promotion of the adoption of safer illuminating paraffin appliances, and second, to mitigate the risks associated with the use of paraffin in households. Furthermore, the respondent stated that the emphasis on evaluating the strength and safety of newly built table-height paraffin stoves reflects a desire to reduce dangers associated with the handling and use of paraffin, fuel, and related equipment.

Participant I: replied that

Responding to the question, the respondent answered that Polokwane Local Municipality has made significant strides in delivering essential services to various areas like Ga-Ramongoana, Rammelwana, Makibelo, Moletjie Moshate, Ga Thoka, Moremadi Park, Ga Mothapo and Mmotong. Services including, human settlements, water and sanitation, roads, and public transportation, electricity and waste management,

reaching these areas indicate effective implementation of DLG strategies.

Participant J: replied that

In response to the question, the respondent shows that PLM has been actively engaged in implementing DLG initiatives, particularly through projects focused on water services and road construction. These projects are intended to transform the well-being of communities and fostering development within the municipality. In addition, the respondent added that the emphasis on water services indicates efforts to enhance essential infrastructure, ensuring residents have access to clean and reliable water sources. Similarly, road construction projects contribute to improved transportation networks, potentially boosting connectivity and accessibility within the municipality.

Results and Discussion

The paper discovered that DLG is effectively implemented in Polokwane Local Municipality. Moreover, it is found that DLG plays an important role in fostering development. DLG further, works with communities towards the realisation of sustainable development. DLG meets the pre-determined needs of the community. DLG has enough capacity to foster the LED Projects. LED empowers the social and economic needs of respective communities at the local level. Community participation is emphasised in all activities of the LED. LED projects fail due to corruption. DLG improves the well-being of the community. LED through DLG stimulates the local economy in the Polokwane Local Municipality. DLG is responsible for empowering and ensuring provision of the independence to the communities. DLG plays an important role in ensuring a sufficient budget for the implementation of LED. DLG ensures proper communication from the promotion and implementation of LED. Polokwane Local Municipality works with its communities towards the achievement of the LED. DLG is responsible for creating employment opportunities through the implementation of LED. There is monitoring and evaluation of the activities of DLG when implementing LED programmes. There are sufficient funds or budget for DLG to support the implementation of LED programmes.

Socio-economic development is promoted through the provision of municipal services such as water, electricity, transportation, and housing and job creation. Unemployment and poverty are alleviated through empowering the informal traders. The Municipality generates money through tourism, agriculture, and Peter Mokaba Stadium for hosting soccer teams. Mining is used for local economic stimulation. The municipality engaged all role players in allowing the investors to implement the Greenery Mall for job opportunities and business attraction. The shortage of skills, unclear municipal policies, poverty, high unemployment rate, and maladministration hinder the effective implementation of LED. Community members are affected by load-shedding. The increase in population is the reason why not all community needs are catered to. A municipality works with the police services and the Seshego Community Against Crime Against Gangsterism to fight drug abuse and crime. LED uses institutional, environmental, and human resources in place to promote local employment opportunities

Recommendations and Conclusion

The paper recommends that the concept of DLG should be enforced

and facilitated to ensure that there is socio-economic and political development in communities of the country, particularly PLM. This paper further, recommends effective community participation and stakeholders to ensure that the utilisation of local resources through the DLG is enforced. In addition, the paper recommends that the local government of South Africa put more emphasis on DLG to enhance the effective municipal projects in the delivery of service and promotion of the well-being of the communities. From the findings, the paper recommends that since the state of DLG is good, the municipality should invest more in the utilization of local resources to deliver the socio-political and economic needs of the community since other respondents are grieving in terms of the poor state of DLG, the municipality should improve and provide for projects that are responsible for catering to the needs of the communities. The paper proposes that municipalities in South Africa empower their communities through education and training as a way of giving them opportunities for the improvement of their area and the state of DLG.

More projects for housing inter alia, should be implemented to improve the local areas of the PLM. Community groups must be emphasised to aid in promoting the state of DLG by fighting the socio-political and economic barriers to enhance effective development in South African municipalities. To maximise the local economy, the paper proposes that local communities be given training in different fields so that their weakness and strength can be exposed. This will help the municipality in finding suitable community members for the municipal projects. Effective leadership to safeguard the state of DLG in Polokwane Local Municipality should be enforced. In recap, to maintain the DLG in Polokwane Local Municipality, community and stakeholder engagement is key in municipal planning and implementation. The paper further recommended the following theory.

The paper proposes the sustainable developmental local economic stimuli Model (SDLESMS) as entails the below principles: participation of community-stakeholder, public/community value, utilisation of local resources, job creation, accountability measures, local education and training, participative NGOs, local investors, and empowerment. This model aims at accelerating and increasing economic growth and employment using local resources to produce a fairer distribution of development is the primary goal of the Sustainable Developmental Local Economic Stimuli Model. To improve public value, the SDLESMS must oversee guaranteeing inclusive local development that welcomes the involvement of NGOs, councils, and community stakeholders. The municipality must facilitate connections among the members of the community. The SDLESMS promotes robust local capacity as a means of enabling growth. The SDLESMS specialises in employment creation through the use of local resources and investment, encouraging community-stakeholder participation in municipal decision-making, providing competent and effective leadership capable of facilitating local development, empowering community members by giving them the necessary social, political, and economic support, and being accountable for promoting public values to guarantee that community members are aligned to their needs and willing to lead the development in their areas. The paper was about the efficacy of developmental local government (DLG) in implementing local economic development strategy (LED), in Polokwane Local Municipality in Limpopo Province. By critiquing the effect of DLG on LED implementation in the Polokwane Local Municipality, the

paper offers insights for policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders involved in local economic development efforts. In essence, DLG is vital for facilitating LED in Polokwane Local Municipality.

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